

Submitted to *Journal of the European Ceramic Society*; March 2015; Revised April 2015.

Aqueous colloidal processing of nano-SiC and its nano-Y₃Al₅O₁₂ liquid-phase sintering additives with carbon nanotubes

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Abstract

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have occasionally been observed to benefit the aqueous colloidal processing of nano-SiC with its nano-Y₃Al₅O₁₂ liquid-phase-sintering additives. Experimental evidence is here presented for a broad set of CNTs with different morphology and/or surface functionalization confirming that CNTs (7 vol.% addition), regardless of their features, prevent the coagulation of these nanoceramic suspensions, whence it is inferred that aqueous colloidal processing is well-suited for the environmentally friendly preparation of the homogeneous mixtures of nanoceramic particles and CNTs required for the fabrication of CNT-reinforced ceramic matrix nanocomposites. Furthermore, it is shown that surface-functionalized CNTs seem to work better than deflocculated CNTs for the preparation of stable concentrated

colloidal suspensions, whose rheological properties are in general very close, but with thinner CNTs being nonetheless preferable. Finally, the feasibility is demonstrated of fabricating SiC/CNT nanocomposites by aqueous colloidal processing followed by liquid-phase assisted spark-plasma sintering.

Keywords: SiC; ceramic/CNT nanocomposites; aqueous colloidal processing; spark-plasma sintering.

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1. Introduction

It is a fact that the widespread use of polycrystalline ceramics, and more particularly of nanoceramics, in many structural applications is strongly limited (or even precluded) by their inherent brittleness, which has motivated intense research activity in the last two decades in the processing of ceramic matrix composites (CMCs), nanostructured or not, reinforced with carbon nanotubes (CNTs) [1-22]. Unfortunately however, two fundamental problems have plagued the successful processing of CNT-reinforced CMCs [17]. One is to achieve the densification of the ceramic matrix without CNT degradation, a problem overcome today by using a rapid sintering technique (although not yet entirely solved for the case of complex-shaped parts). The other is to achieve a homogeneous CNT dispersion within the ceramic matrix, for which it is first critical to prepare well-dispersed mixtures of the CNTs and ceramic powders. This problem, per se intrinsically difficult, becomes especially challenging in the case of ceramic nanopowders due to their much greater specific surface area and interparticle interaction forces, but is amenable to being tackled by aqueous colloidal processing, as demonstrated elsewhere for oxide ceramics [23,24] and for non-oxide ceramics [25]. Importantly, in that last recent study on nano-SiC+nano- $Y_3Al_5O_{12}$ without and with CNTs (10–20 nm thick, 0.5–2 μm length, OH^- surface groups) [25], where $Y_3Al_5O_{12}$ (hereafter abbreviated simply as YAG) is the liquid-phase sintering additive of SiC and the CNTs the reinforcing phase, we observed that the CNT addition improved the rheological behaviour of those suspensions of ceramic nanoparticles, even preventing their otherwise irremediable and irreversible coagulation at high shear rates. If proven more general, this beneficial effect of the CNTs, so far observed just once [25], might have broad implications for the environmentally friendly preparation of either nanoceramic/CNT powder mixtures (by drying or freeze-drying the suspensions) or nanoceramic/CNT components (by wet-

shaping the suspensions), which can then be subjected to rapid densification (by spark-plasma sintering (SPS), microwave sintering, or flash sintering). Consequently, elucidating this issue of generalness is an important question requiring an early answer. This was indeed the central objective of the present study, which was aimed at preparing and characterizing rheologically a greater number of colloidal suspensions of SiC+YAG nanopowders with a much broader set of CNTs having different morphology and/or surface functionalization. As a complement to the rheological study, preliminary SPS results of these SiC/CNT nanocomposites are also presented.

2. Experimental procedure

The starting materials were commercially-available nanopowders of SiC (~45–55 nm particle size) and YAG (~40 nm particle size), as well as seven multiwall CNTs with different morphology and/or surface functionalization (see Table I), all of them supplied by Nanostructured and Amorphous Materials Inc (USA). They were used in their as-received condition with no further treatment. In particular, thin-CNTs, ref-CNTs, and thick-CNTs were used to investigate the possible effect of the CNT thickness on the rheological behaviour of the nanoceramic suspensions. The possible effect of the CNT length was investigated using ref-CNTs and long-CNTs. And finally, the possible effect of the CNT surface functionalization was investigated using nsg-CNTs, ref-CNTs, and acid-CNTs, as well as long-CNTs and g-CNTs. These commercially-available CNTs were synthesized by catalytic chemical vapour deposition, and have been characterized in detail by the manufacturer using a wide battery of analytical techniques.

The colloidal stability of the nanopowders (SiC and YAG) and CNTs was studied individually on dilute suspensions (0.1 g/l) with a short equilibrium time (30 min). Specifically,

systematic zeta potential measurements (Zetasizer Nano-ZS, Malvern, UK) were done as a function of pH (adjusted in the acidic or basic range using 10^{-1} M HCl or KOH solution, respectively) on suspensions prepared without deflocculant using deionised water and ethanol mixed in a 9:1 volume ratio as suspension medium and KCl 10^{-2} M as inert electrolyte. Selected zeta potential measurements were also carried out as a function of the deflocculant content (in the range 0–5 wt%) at natural pH, but only for the nanopowders of SiC and YAG and for those CNTs that were found to be poorly dispersible; in all cases, deflocculation was done using commercially-available polyelectrolytes, in particular, a synthetic polyelectrolyte of unknown composition (Produkt KV5088, Zschimmer-Schwarz, Germany) for nano-SiC, an ammonium polyacrylate (PAA; DuramaxTM D-3005, Rohm & Haas, USA) for nano-YAG, and a polyester/polyamine condensation polymer (Hypermer KD-7, Croda, USA) for the CNTs.

Multi-component suspensions containing 93 vol.% nanopowder (in particular 90 wt% nano-SiC and 10 wt% nano-YAG) plus 7 vol.% CNTs were then prepared to a 5 vol.% of total solid loading, in the same combination of water and ethanol as before. Ethanol was intentionally introduced to reduce the surface tension of the suspension media (water and ethanol surface tensions at 25 °C are ~ 72 and $22 \text{ mN}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$, respectively), and thus to favour the dispersion. The suspension pH was adjusted to the desired value by dropwise addition of an aqueous solution of 25 wt% tetramethylammonium hydroxide (TMAH, Aldrich-Chemie, Germany). The suspensions were prepared under continuous stirring as follows. Firstly, if needed, KD-7 was added to the solution, followed by incorporation of the CNTs and sonication up to dispersion. Then, PAA was added as needed to disperse the YAG nanoparticles, followed by addition of the YAG nanopowder and sonication for 1 min. Lastly, PKV was added as required to disperse the SiC

nanoparticles, followed by addition of the SiC nanopowder and sonication for different times, which was done so as to investigate its influence on the rheological behaviour.

The rheological behaviour of the resulting suspensions was then evaluated at 25 °C using a rheometer (MARS, Haake, Thermo, Germany) with a double-cone/plate configuration (DC60/2°, Haake, Thermo) operated in controlled shear rate mode with the following measurement cycle: linear increase of the shear rate from 0 to 1000 s⁻¹ in 300 s, plateau at 1000 s⁻¹ for 60 s, and decrease to zero shear rate in 300 s. The thixotropy or the rheopexy was determined from the area of the hysteresis loop of the flow curve.

Well-dispersed suspensions of nano-SiC+nano-YAG+CNTs were then frozen within a rotavap (RV10 basic, IKA, Germany) immersed in a liquid-N₂ bath and next freeze-dried (Cryodos-50, Telstar, Spain) at -50 °C and 0.3 mPa, after which the resulting powder mixtures were examined by scanning (SEM; Quanta 3D FEG, FEI, The Netherlands) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM; Tecnai G2-20 Twin, FEI, The Netherlands) at 15 and 200 kV accelerating voltage, respectively. Finally, one of these powder mixtures was also densified by SPS (Dr. Sinter SPS-2050, Sumitomo Coal Mining Co., Japan), under the following conditions: atmosphere of dynamic vacuum, peak temperature of 1700 °C, heating ramp of 100 °C·min⁻¹, soaking time of 5 min, and uniaxial pressure of 75 MPa. Lastly, the SPS-ed ceramic was characterized using SEM and Raman spectroscopy (Nicolet Almega XR, Thermo Scientific, UK), the former used for routine microstructural observations and the latter to assess the survival of the CNTs at these SPS conditions. Note that the present study is mainly focused on aspects of aqueous colloidal processing, and that a wider parametric investigation of the effect of the SPS conditions on the microstructure-properties of these SiC/CNT nanocomposites is deferred to

later reports, reason for which only selected SPS results are anticipated here to confirm the processing's feasibility.

3. Results and discussion

Figure 1 shows the zeta potential value as a function of pH for the individual dilute suspensions of nano-SiC, nano-YAG, and seven different types of CNTs. Results for nano-SiC and nano-YAG are taken from an earlier study [25], and will therefore be discussed here only briefly as needed for establishing the optimal dispersing conditions of the multi-component concentrated suspensions. Specifically, SiC and YAG nanoparticles have their isoelectric points at pH \sim 5.3 and 8.8, respectively. The former reflects that the surface of the SiC nanoparticles is only partially passivated [25], whereas the latter is the expectation for a Y_2O_3 - Al_2O_3 mixed oxide [25-27]. It can also be seen in Fig. 1 that the CNTs exhibit the same general trend, all having their surface negatively charged at natural pH and zeta potential values nearly constant and greater (in absolute value) than -25 mV at basic pH's and in general at neutral pH as well. Natural pH's were measured to be 4.64, 4.65, 5.17, 5.08, 4.83, 6.20, and 5.00 for ref-CNTs, thin-CNTs, thick-CNTs, long-CNTs, acid-CNTs, nsg-CNTs, and g-CNTs, respectively. The isoelectric points all occur at acidic pH's, and in particular at pH's in the range 1–2, except for nsg-CNTs for which it occurs at pH \sim 3. Another distinctive feature of nsg-CNTs in relation to the rest of the CNTs that was noted during the preparation of the dilute suspensions was their poorer dispersion behaviour, attributable to the absence of surface functionalization; this is in good agreement with the lower absolute zeta potential of nsg-CNTs, which in addition do not reach the value -25 mV up to basic pH \sim 9. Therefore, nsg-CNTs need deflocculant addition to avoid their undesirable agglomeration. Consequently, when using the nsg-CNTs, 1 wt% of the

polyelectrolyte KD-7 will be added to the suspensions. This is an appropriate content because, as shown in Fig. 2, the zeta potential does not vary noticeably with the KD-7 content (1–5 wt%), and the KD-7 addition is needed to improve the dispersibility of nsg-CNTs (a fact also confirmed experimentally on the multi-component concentrated suspensions). With this information, the multi-component concentrated suspensions were then prepared at basic pH (pH \sim 10) using the following combination of deflocculant contents: 4 wt% PKV for the SiC nanoparticles, 2 wt% PAA for the YAG nanoparticles, and 1 wt% KD-7 for the nsg-CNTs; for the rest of the CNTs, no KD-7 was added. A detailed justification of the choice of these PKV and PAA contents is given elsewhere [25], and is therefore not provided here.

The flow curves of all multi-component concentrated suspensions of nano-SiC+nano-YAG+CNTs exhibited the same general trends with sonication time that will be discussed next for a selected case by way of example. In particular, Fig. 3 compares the flow curves measured for the suspension of nano-SiC+nano-YAG+long-CNTs sonicated for 2, 3, and 5 min. It can be seen that for short sonication times (i.e., 2 and 3 min) the flow curves exhibit a broad rheopexy cycle that is associated with the suspension having a shear-thickening rheological behaviour that induces increasing viscosities due to the formation of strong network structures. Eventually the scenario changes after a certain sonication time (i.e., 5 min) at and above which the flow curves already exhibit a sharp thixotropy cycle that reflects the suspension having a slight shear-thinning rheological behaviour. It is important to mention that this rheopexy-to-thixotropy change (or, which is the same, shear-thickening-to-shear-thinning behaviour change) has not been observed in the counterpart suspension without CNTs (i.e., only of nano-SiC+nano-YAG), at least up to the 7-min sonication time investigated [25], which is clear evidence that the addition of CNTs, whichever their particular morphology, and once they are appropriately

dispersed, prevents the coagulation of these ceramic suspensions. This occurs because CNTs act efficiently as physical barriers against the aggregation of the ceramic nanoparticles, first, when at low shear rates they are already untangled, by separating the nanoparticles, and then, when at high shear rates they are stretched and unfurled, by further dispersing the nanoparticles [25].

Nonetheless, in rheological terms, two types of CNTs were found experimentally to affect the suspension properties more appreciably than the rest. In particular, Fig. 4 shows the values of the hysteresis loop and of the critical shear rate for coagulation of the suspensions as a function of sonication time, determined from the analysis of the flow curves. Recall that the critical shear rate for coagulation has been defined to be the value of shear rate in the flow curve at which suspension viscosity suddenly increases, thus dictating the onset of a new colloidal region with solid-like behaviour due to the formation of a network structure [25]. Clearly, Fig. 4 reveals a complex nonlinear dependence of both magnitudes on the sonication, with a change in the trend at a certain sonication time that in general is in the interval 2–3 min; the exceptions are the suspensions with thin-CNTs and nsg-CNTs, the former not exhibiting this change and the latter exhibiting it later (i.e., 4–5 min). This complex rheological behaviour suggests that there is a certain digestion time at which the laminar flow regime changes, attributable to a change in the suspension structure. Distinctively, the suspensions with thin-CNTs and nsg-CNTs are, respectively, by far the least and the most prone to coagulate, a highly undesirable phenomenon for the wet-shaping of these ceramic/CNT nanocomposites. The former is attributable to the greater specific surface area available for the CNTs to physically separate the ceramic nanoparticles (given that the volume fraction of CNTs was kept constant), and is especially relevant because it breaks the conventional wisdom in the field that the thinner the CNTs the more difficult their dispersion. The latter is noteworthy because, unlike the other CNTs that were

all sonicated for only 1 min prior to the addition of the rest of suspension components, nsg-CNTs were sonicated for 5 min, despite which the resulting suspensions behave more poorly. It can thus be inferred that a key requirement for the correct dispersion of CNTs in ceramic matrices is their chemical covalent functionalization, which at least in the present study worked better than their non-covalent functionalization in the form of physical adsorption of a certain surfactant on the CNT surface. Interestingly, the addition of the vast majority of the CNTs (i.e., ref-, thick-, long-, acid-, g-CNTs) resulted in ceramic suspensions with closely similar rheological properties, which must be interpreted positively due to its important implications (i.e., there is no dependence of the processing conditions on the CNT features) for the commercial mass development of these products by the advanced ceramic industry.

Having prepared a broad set of different stable concentrated suspensions of nano-SiC+nano-YAG+CNTs, the next step to further corroborate the applicability of proposed dispersion procedure was to select one of them in particular, for example the suspension nano-SiC+nano-YAG+ref-CNTs, for the preparation of SiC matrix nanocomposites reinforced with CNTs. In this regard, Fig. 5 shows **representative SEM and TEM micrographs** of the powder mixture of ceramic nanoparticles and CNTs obtained by freeze-drying the selected suspension, which confirms the good dispersion of the different phases. According to the densification curve logged during SPS (not shown), this powder mixture resulted in a fully-dense composite at the conditions of 1700 °C for 5 min under 75 MPa. Also, the SEM micrographs of the fracture surface of the broken specimen, such as the one presented in Fig. 6, confirm its complete densification while showing that the microstructure comprises what appears to be CNTs homogeneously distributed among SiC nanograins in turn surrounded by a YAG intergranular phase. The Raman spectrum of the sintered nanocomposite shown in Fig. 7 confirms the

presence of the three characteristic bands associated with CNTs (D-band at $\sim 1360\text{ cm}^{-1}$, G-band at $\sim 1595\text{ cm}^{-1}$, and 2D-band at $\sim 2717\text{ cm}^{-1}$), with intensity ratios I_D/I_G and I_{2D}/I_D of 0.47 and 0.88, respectively, which reflect that these CNTs have high purity and structural quality [28], and therefore that they have survived the SPS. This proves that, despite the complex rheological behaviour exhibited by ceramic nanoparticles and CNTs, it is possible to prepare dense, homogeneous SiC matrix nanocomposites reinforced with CNTs by aqueous colloidal processing together with liquid-phase assisted SPS.

4. Concluding remarks

We have used aqueous colloidal processing for the environmentally friendly preparation of a broad set (i.e., seven) of stable concentrated suspensions (i.e., 5 vol.% of total solid loading) of homogeneous mixtures of SiC and YAG nanoparticles (93 vol.% content) with CNTs (7 vol.% content) of different morphology and surface functionalization. We have shown that CNTs, if properly dispersed, and regardless of their features, prevent the undesirable coagulation of these nanoceramic suspensions, thus obtaining multi-component suspensions with adequate rheological properties. It emerges therefore that aqueous colloidal processing is clearly functional for the wet shaping of ceramic/CNT nanocomposite green-bodies, or alternatively for the preparation of the corresponding powder mixtures, both of which could then be densified by liquid-phase assisted rapid sintering without CNT degradation (as demonstrated here by SPS at 1700 °C for 5 min under 75 MPa). Interestingly, we also observed that, for the suspension preparation, it seems impractical to use the combination of non-functionalized CNTs plus deflocculant (specifically KD-7) over surface-functionalized CNTs. Moreover, the latter lead to suspensions with closely similar rheological properties, a highly-desirable attribute in industry,

although thinner CNTs are nonetheless preferable.

Acknowledgements This work was supported by the Ministerio de Economía y Competitividad (Government of Spain) and FEDER Funds under Grant N° MAT 2010-16848. Funding of the project N° MAT 2013-41012-P is also gratefully acknowledged. VMC also thanks the Government of Spain for supporting his stay at the University of Stockholm through the grant N° EEBB-I-13-07128.

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Figure captions

Figure 1. Dependence on pH of the zeta potential for the individual, dilute suspensions of the different raw powders (i.e., nano-SiC [24], nano-YAG [24], and seven types of CNTs). Lines are to guide the eye.

Figure 2. Dependence on deflocculant content (KD-7) of the zeta potential for the individual, dilute suspensions of the nsg-CNTs, at natural pH and pH 10. Lines are to guide the eye.

Figure 3. Selected flow curves of the concentrated suspension of nano-SiC+nano-YAG+long-CNTs with sonication times of 2, 3 and 5 min.

Figure 4. Dependence on sonication time of (A) hysteresis loop and (B) critical shear for coagulation for the entire set of concentrated suspensions of nano-SiC+nano-YAG+CNTs; the specific type of CNTs used is indicated in the label. Lines are to guide the eye. In (A), the regions of rheopexy and thixotropy have been distinguished. In (B), the sonication times cover the corresponding intervals of shear-thickening behaviour, where coagulation may occur.

Figure 5. Representative (A) SEM and (B) TEM micrographs of the powder mixture obtained by freeze-drying the concentrated suspension of nano-SiC+nano-YAG+ref-CNTs subjected to 4 min of sonication. Arrows in (A) point to some CNTs.

Figure 6. Representative SEM micrograph of the microstructure (fracture surface of the broken specimen) of the SiC/CNT nanocomposite prepared by aqueous colloidal processing (freeze-

drying of the suspension nano-SiC+nano-YAG+ref-CNTs subjected to 4 min of sonication) followed by liquid-phase assisted SPS. The inset shows a magnified region. Arrows point to some CNTs. Evidences of CNT pullout are also seen.

Figure 7. Raman spectrum of the SiC/CNT nanocomposites prepared by aqueous colloidal processing followed by liquid-phase assisted SPS. The peak indexing is indicated.

Table caption

Table I. Main characteristics of the seven types of CNTs used.

CNT designation	CNT features [#]			
	Length (μm)	Thickness (nm)	Surface functionalization	Specific surface area (m^2g^{-1})
thin-CNTs	0.5–2	8–15	OH^-	> 235
ref-CNTs	0.5–2	10–20	OH^-	> 200
thick-CNTs	0.5–2	50–80	OH^-	> 40
long-CNTs	10–30	10–20	OH^-	> 200
nsg-CNTs	0.5–2	10–20	none	> 200
acid-CNTs	0.5–2	10–20	COOH^-	> 200
g-CNTs	10–30	10–20	graphitized	> 100

[#] According to the manufacturer's specifications. A more detailed characterization of these CNTs (techniques used can be TEM, SEM, X-ray photoemission spectroscopy, energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy, thermal analysis, and inductively coupled plasma spectroscopy) is available in the manufacturer's website.

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Figure 4

